

inDICES

Measuring the Impact of Digital Culture

Deliverable 3.6

inDICES Policy Brief Executive Summary

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Towards Community-Focused Cultural Heritage Institutions Operating With Purpose in the Digital Realm

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This is a set of policy recommendations designed to assist cultural heritage institutions (CHIs) in fulfilling their public mission in the digital realm: to further the democratic and community-focused digital transformation of CHIs, and to support access to, and the reusability of, digital cultural heritage, to better prepare CHIs for the digital transformation. The recommendations are authored by inDICES¹, a Horizon 2020 research project, however it is the end result of an inclusive, collaborative process led by inDICE partners and over fifty Europe-based heritage professionals.

The recommendations come in the context of major transitions under way in the cultural heritage sector (with COVID-19 spurring the need for new, hybrid models) and are intended to be implemented at the local, national, or European level by the key stakeholders of digital cultural heritage policies.

Recommendations

The brief puts forth a total of fifteen recommendations, grouped into recommendation areas centred around five overarching themes:

1. CHIs should anchor their public mission in the digital realm

The first, main recommendation area addresses the ways CHIs can respond to the challenges of digital transformation. This will involve embracing digital at all levels of their operations and understanding their role in building relations with their communities. CHIs should be given the freedom to experiment and assume risk as they tailor their digital transformation to their core mission, resources, and relevant communities. They must also communicate, in a clear and understandable fashion, how cultural heritage can be shared and reused under current copyright law. Finally, they require continuous and long-term financial backing to pursue their public mission in the digital realm.

To accomplish the above, inDICES recommends that **appropriate impact assessment mechanisms and evaluation processes be introduced in CHIs**. Cultural heritage professionals should design new KPIs and impact indicators to enable stakeholders to understand the social and economic effect of digital transformation in their sectors.

Secondly, **capacity building opportunities for CHIs should be created and expanded to empower their operations in the digital realm**. These efforts should focus on training CHI

¹ <https://indices-culture.eu/>

professionals with the knowledge, competencies, and skills they need to be fully operational in the digital realm.

Finally, it is necessary to encourage the **greater reuse of cultural heritage by facilitating cross-sectoral knowledge exchange, dialogue, and collaboration** between researchers, educators, creators, and tech experts. Bigger heritage networks should act as hubs to raise awareness, drive the creation of participatory platforms, and spark interaction between professionals from various domains.

2. Empower democratic and community-focused CHIs

The second recommendation area addresses the need for CHIs to become genuinely community-focused, participation-oriented, and focused on the needs of their users, which requires the integration of democratisation processes based on inclusivity and equity. CHIs must also acknowledge their roles in creating opportunities for their communities to co-create and reuse heritage collections, and thus transition away from their previous roles as knowledge gatekeepers.

inDICES recommends that **CHIs review and enhance their operational principles and practices to support participation, co-creation and community focus**. Cultural heritage institutions will need to be given the freedom and ability to create new, inclusive models and procedures, which may require the creation of new professional roles or the strengthening of existing ones.

Furthermore, CHIs must be **encouraged to create innovative labs to foster the participatory reuse of digital heritage**. These creative spaces would create opportunities to experiment and innovate in collaboration with creators, tech experts, and other communities. To make this possible, the legal and organisational frames of publicly funded CHIs would have to be revised to permit a greater tolerance for risk.

Finally, reliable **frameworks for digital community engagement should be developed** and provided to CHIs, enabling them to better understand new or evolving digital heritage communities.

3. Prioritise purposeful digitisation supporting reuse of cultural heritage collections

The heritage sector should adopt a more purposeful, high-quality approach to digitisation, prioritising collections open for reuse. The process itself must become more inclusive, taking into account the needs of all concerned stakeholders.

It is recommended that **digitisation funding programmes and policies facilitating reuse be prioritised**, also through new EU legal instruments ensuring access and (re)use of cultural heritage resources.

Secondly, **infrastructures should be combined**, allowing the most well-equipped CHIs to host the required IT infrastructure, and decoupling the intellectual management of collections from their technical administration.

Finally, **CHIs must ensure the participatory character of their digitisation strategies.** They will have to leverage their knowledge of intellectual property rights, impact assessments, and dialogue to develop more democratic, community-focused approaches to digitisation.

4. Make the heritage sector a pillar of the European digital public space

The heritage sector should support the establishment of an interoperable, public ecosystem for cultural and creative content, with public, civic and grassroots infrastructures, platforms and services playing the main role. This will require the transformation of organisational cultures, and should be created with funding provided in the Digital Europe programme.

Shared standards must be adopted to accelerate the interoperability of digital heritage collections. Instead of creating disconnected, unsustainable platforms that will eventually become obsolete, the cultural heritage sector should support the establishment of strong interoperability rules and standards for digitised and born-digital collections alike.

Moreover, it is necessary to **foster the development of the common European data space for cultural heritage.** CHIs should aspire to develop best practices to make heritage data and content interoperable, and eventually work to create a broader digital public space.

Finally, **CHIs should be encouraged to play an active role in exploring the creation of participatory platforms which support reuse.** Drawing on the experiences with community engagement and participatory online spaces developed in their current practice, CHIs should contribute to the development of future non-commercial platforms, services, and apps.

5. Design a model for ethical cultural heritage practices

More responsible, ethical, and democratic curatorial strategies are needed for CHIs to fulfil their mission to provide access to collections while upholding their responsibility to manage the way objects and data are shared. Institutions should discuss at an international level how to integrate ethical guidelines into the daily operations of heritage professionals.

To start, CHIs must **identify and address current ethical questions relevant to the heritage sector** by establishing, for example, a cross-sectoral think tank to facilitate dialogue on issues that include access to content, climate sustainability, treatment of sensitive content, decolonising collections, and links to new technology.

Moreover, **CHIs must revisit their ethical strategies** to identify best practices as well as existing weaknesses, particularly in regard to sensitive content, and subsequently disseminate streamlined ethical guidelines.

Finally, it is necessary to **empower a stewardship mindset in CHIs**, which involves heritage professionals moving away from their traditional roles as gatekeepers and instead embracing the role of stewards of collections and knowledge.